

ANALYZING THE SHEAR PERFORMANCE OF SFRC BEAMS WITH GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER AS LONGITUDINAL REBARS

Gabriela Mazureki Campos Bahniuk, Federal University of Paraná, Brazil, gabriela.campos@uepg.br
Ricardo Pieralisi, Federal University of Paraná, Brazil, ricpialisi@ufpr.br
Roberto Dalledone Machado, Federal University of Paraná, Brazil, rdm@ufpr.br

ABSTRACT

This research aims to investigate the shear behaviour of SFRC beams reinforced with longitudinal GFRP rebars without stirrups. Eight SFRC beams of dimensions (15x30x205) cm and various volume fractions of steel fibers (0, 0.5%, 0.75% and 1.0%) were cast, maintaining a constant shear-span-to-depth ratio ($a/d = 3.0$) and compressive strength of 70 MPa. Three-point bending tests were conducted and vertical deflections were monitored using LVDTs. The study focused on evaluating the crack pattern, failure mode, and load-deflection behaviour. Additionally, the experimental shear capacity was compared with shear strength predictions obtained from different codes and models.

KEYWORDS

Steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC); Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) rebars; Shear; Reinforced concrete without stirrups.

INTRODUCTION

The utilization of a combination of steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC) with glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) rebars provides an alternative solution for structural beams, eliminating the need for conventional stirrups.

FRP bars offer significant potential for practical applications. They possess several advantageous properties, such as corrosion resistance, high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent fatigue resistance, non-magnetic nature, and low electrical and thermal conductivity when compared to steel bars (Jafarzadeh & Nematzadeh, 2020). However, one limitation of using FRP bars in structural elements is that the bends must be incorporated during manufacturing and cannot be performed after the resin has cured (Nanni, De Luca & Zadeh, 2014). Shear behavior of FRP bars is primarily influenced by the properties of the matrix, resulting in relatively lower shear strengths. Additionally, the utilization of traditional stirrups as transverse reinforcement in reinforced concrete structures may have long-term performance impact (Soltanzadeh et al., 2016). Consequently, the incorporation of discrete steel fibers in beams presents a viable solution to eliminate the need for transverse reinforcement.

The evaluation of fiber-reinforced beams' behavior against shear forces dates back to 1972, with subsequent studies consistently demonstrating that the inclusion of steel fibers enhances the shear strength of concrete beams (Barros & Foster, 2018). Substituting stirrups with discrete fibers to resist shear offers numerous advantages. Firstly, the random distribution of fibers being throughout the concrete element ensures resistance in all directions. Additionally, this approach reduces labor-intensive process of bending and positioning traditional stirrups while accommodating different cross-sectional configurations (Imam et al., 1997). Consequently, steel fibers in concrete have been widely employed as either primary or secondary reinforcement in structural elements, as recommend by various codes and guidelines. Notable examples include RILEM TC 162-TDF (Réunion Internationale Des Laboratoires et Experts des Matériaux [RILEM], 2003), FIB Model Code (Federation Internationale du Beton [FIB], 2010), CNR-DT 203 (National Research Council, 2006), ACI 318-08 (American Concrete Institute [ACI], 2007), NBR 16935 (Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas [ABNT], 2021).

Significant contributions to understanding the behavior of FRP bar-reinforced beams, incorporating discrete steel fibers in various volumes and geometries, have been made by several researchers. Ferrier et al. (2015), Yoo, Banthia and Yoon (2016a), Yoo, Banthia and Yoon (2016b), Soltanzadeh et al. (2016), Vakili, Homami and Esfahani (2019), Tran, Pham and Hao (2020), Hosseini, Nematzadeh and Chastre (2021), Nematzadeh and Fallah-Valukolaee (2021) and Aydın, Boru and Aydın (2021) have conducted comprehensive studies in this domain. These investigations focused on beams reinforced with different types of FRP bars (GFRP, CFRP, BFRP), without stirrups. Additionally, they explored the effects of discrete steel fibers on the behavior of the beams. Several of these studies have even proposed models for predicting the shear strength of reinforced concrete beams with FRP bars and discrete steel fibers.

In this sense, the objective of this study is to investigate the shear behaviour of SFRC concrete beams reinforced with longitudinal GFRP rebars. Furthermore, the experimental shear capacity obtained from the tests conducted are compared with shear strength predictions derived from different codes, guidelines and previous research findings.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Material properties

In this research, SFRC is used in the fabrication of the beams. The concrete composition included CPV-ARI cement (Type III - ASTM C150/C150M), limestone filler, natural sand (fineness modulus of 1.87 and a density of 2.630 kg/m³), coarse diabase aggregate (maximum size of 12,5 mm and a density of 2.990 kg/m³), water and superplasticizer additive PowerFlow 1180 by MC-Bauchemie. The discrete steel fibers utilized is Belgo Bekaert - DRAMIX 3D 65/35 BG with hooked ends (see Figure 1a). These fibers have a form factor of 65, length of 35 mm, diameter of 0.55 mm and tensile strength of 1345 MPa. Table 1 presents the concrete mix. Notably, the inclusion of steel fibers resulted in variations in the content of coarse aggregate, consequently affecting the amount of superplasticizer incorporated into the concrete.

Table 1: Mix design of concrete

Beam	Concrete mix design (kg/m ³)						V _f (%)	Superplasticizer (%)
	Cement	Limestone filler	Water	Sand	Coarse aggregate	Steel fiber		
CC0	436	70	183.1	872	959.2	0	0	0
SFRC0.50	436	70	183.1	872	946.1	39.25	0.50	1.4
SFRC0.75	436	70	183.1	872	937.4	58.88	0.75	1.6
SFRC1.00	436	70	183.1	872	928.7	78.50	1.00	1.7

For flexural reinforcement, GFRP rebars, provided by Haizer Building Group – Brazil, with nominal diameters of 10 mm are employed (see Figure 1b). The mechanical properties of these rebars IS obtained through tension tests conducted in accordance with ASTM D7205 (American Society for Testing and Materials [ASTM], 2016). According to the tests, Young's modulus, tensile strength, and elongation at failure of the GFRP bars are 50.65 GPa, 978.4 MPa, and 1.95%, respectively.

a) Steel fibers

b) GFRP

Figure 1: Steel fibers and GFRP used in the study.

Specimens and test setup

In the study of the beams, the independent variable manipulated during the tests is the volume of steel fibers incorporated into the concrete. The analysis involves three different volumes: 0.5 %, 0.75 % and 1.0 %, in addition to a reference concrete sample without fibers. The compressive strength of the concrete and the longitudinal reinforcement rate of GFRP (consisting of three 10 mm diameter bars) are kept constant as fixed parameters. A total of eight SFRC beams are casted, each with dimensions (15×30×205) cm, with a concrete compressive strength of approximately 70 MPa. Two beams are cast for each fiber volume. Figure 2 provides details of the cross-section, longitudinal section, three-point loading test, and support positioning. Vertical deflection beneath the concentrated load is measured using LVDT. The shear span “a” measured 94.5 cm on one side and 81 cm on the other, resulting in shear span-to-depth ratios (a/d) of 3.5 and 3.0, respectively. The supports are intentionally positioned asymmetrically to ensure shear failure occurred on the desired side, considering that stirrups are not placed on the beams. The expected load for the flexural capacity of the GFRP-SFRC beams is 140 kN. Figure 3 illustrates the beam during the test. The tests are conducted using an Instron press, model EMIC 23-300 with a nominal capacity of 300 kN. The piston displacement is controlled at a rate of 0.5 mm/min.

Figure 2: Details of the test setup

Figure 3: Setup for loading test

As concrete has characteristics of self-compacting concrete (Figure 4a), in the fresh state, the slump-flow is determined by the Abrams cone method, according to the recommendations of NBR 15823-1 (ABNT, 2017) and NBR 15823-2 (ABNT, 2017). The mechanical characterization hardened state of each mix is performed through the following tests: compressive strength on six cylindrical specimens of $\phi 100 \times 200$ mm (NBR 5739 – ABNT, 2018); modulus of elasticity on four cylindrical specimens of $\phi 100 \times 200$ mm (NBR 8522-1 – ABNT, 2021); and flexural tensile strength on six prismatic specimens of $150 \times 150 \times 550$ mm (NBR 16940 – ABNT, 2022). All these hardened state tests are conducted at 28 days of age. Table 2 presents the average results of slump-flow, compressive strength (f_{cm}), flexural

tensile strength ($f_{ct,f}$), modulus of elasticity (E_c), and residual strengths (f_{R1} , f_{R2} , f_{R3} , f_{R4}). The standard deviation (s) is also presented in parentheses for the four mixes studied.

The nomenclature used for the beams are CC for conventional concrete (without fibers) and SFRC for steel fiber reinforced concrete, followed by the indication of the volume fractions of steel fibers (V_f) adopted.

Table 2: Properties of beam concrete

Beam	V_f (%)	Slump-flow (mm)	f_{cm} (MPa)	$f_{ct,f}$ (MPa)	E_c (GPa)	$f_{R,1}$ (MPa)	$f_{R,2}$ (MPa)	$f_{R,3}$ (MPa)	$f_{R,4}$ (MPa)
CC0	0	260	73.2 (6.39)	5.97 (0.69)	47.79 (1.69)	-	-	-	-
SFRC0.50	0.50	255	75.65 (2.62)	-	46.80 (1.82)	6.7 (0.40)	5.6 (0.42)	4.2 (0.25)	3.4 (0.17)
SFRC0.75	0.75	235	70.2 (7.06)	-	47.18 (3.17)	8.7 (1.33)	7.3 (1.18)	5.6 (0.93)	4.6 (0.76)
SFRC1.00	1.00	220	71.6 (3.57)	-	52.86 (0.72)	9.9 (0.73)	7.8 (0.65)	5.8 (0.56)	4.8 (0.53)

The pouring point of the concrete into the forms is chosen to be in the central region (Figure 4b). Given the fluidity of the concrete, all specimens and beams are compacted solely through external vibration using a rubber hammer (Figure 4c). Regarding the beams, they are demolded 48 hours after casting. Within 24 hours, the upper surface of the beams is moistened and covered with a damp drainage mat and plastic sheeting. From that point until 28 days, the beams are moistened on a daily basis (Figure 4d).

Figure 4: Depicts the casting methods and procedure of beams

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Failure mode and cracking behavior

Figure 5 illustrates the types of failure observed in the beams and provides insight into their cracking behavior. Since stirrups are not utilized in the beams, the predominant failure mode for most beams is shear failure, resulting in sudden rupture in the smaller span. However, it is worth noting that the SFRC0.75-2 beam exhibited failure in the larger span, which may be attributed to the internal distribution of steel fibers. Further investigations should be conducted to analyze the fiber orientation within the beams in more detail. For SFRC1.00-2 beam, a failure from shear to flexure-shear can be considered, because only for this beam the maximum load recorded is higher than the expected load for the flexural capacity as well as there is no sudden failure.

Cracking initiation occurred at the bottom of the beam, precisely in the region experiencing the maximum moment, where these cracks predominantly exhibited a vertical orientation. As the load increased, flexural cracks are observed in the spans. However, considering the low shear strength, these cracks gradually transitioned into more inclined orientation until reaching failure, where they extended to the loading point. Beams with the same fiber volumes displayed similar crack configurations.

Figure 5: Failure modes and cracking pattern in tested beams at failure

Load-deflection behavior

Table 3 presents the results obtained from testing all beams, while Figure 6 illustrates the load-deflection behavior exhibited by the tested beams, demonstrating a predominantly bilinear relationship.

Table 3: Summary of experimental results

Beam		f_{cm} (MPa)	P_u (kN)	V_u (kN)	δ_u^* (mm)	$\delta_{maximum}$ (mm)	Failure
CC0	1	76.9	61.3	34.0	12.29	13.34	Shear
	2	69.4	52.7	29.4	11.81	12.37	Shear
	Average	73.15	-	31.7	-	12.86	-
SFRC0.50	1	77.0	123.8	67.6	21.32	23.41	Shear
	2	74.3	107.9	59.1	17.52	19.29	Shear
	Average	75.65	-	63.35	-	21.35	-
SFRC0.75	1	73.5	119.4	65.3	24.27	24.57	Shear
	2	66.9	131.8	72.0	21.10	24.45	Shear
	Average	70.2	-	68.65	-	24.51	-
SFRC1.00	1	71.3	121.0	66.1	19.51	19.77	Shear
	2	71.9	157.6	85.9	40.97	42.26	Flexure-Shear
	Average	71.6	-	76.0	-	31.02	-

P_u : last load
 δ_u : displacement at P_u

Figure 6: Load x deflection of tested beams

The load-deflection curves indicate that as the proportion of fiber volume increases, there is a noticeable upward shift, leading to improved load capacity, stiffness, and deflection at peak load of the beams (see Table 4). For example, the SFRC1.0-2 beam experienced an almost 300 % increase in load capacity with the addition of fibers when compared to the CC0-1 beam results. The addition of fibers in the concrete effectively contributed to load transfer in the tensile region.

Considering the average shear capacity between the two beams tested for each fiber volume, there is an overall increase in load capacity as the fiber volume increases. Examining the beams with the same fiber volume, it is observed that the difference in shear capacity is 15.7 % for the CC0 beams, 14.4 %

for the SFRC0.50 beams, 10.3 % for SFRC0.75 beams and 30 % for SFRC1.00 beams. Additionally, a significant difference in vertical deflection at the peak load is observed among the SFRC1.00 beams, ranging from 19.77 mm to 42.26 mm. In constraint, the vertical deflection at the peak load of the beams is similar for other fiber volumes.

ANALYTICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determining shear capacity

Various theoretical models have been presented in different codes to estimate the shear capacity of beams with FRP rebars or SFRC beams. These models are outlined in Table 4. Additionally, researchers have developed their own models that consider the combination of SFRC and FRP bars. Table 5 presents the shear strength results obtained using these methodologies. Table 6 provides a summary of the ratios between the different models and methodologies. The standard deviation (s) is also presented in parentheses for the average.

Table 4: Various models available for shear strength of FRP beams, SFRC beams and SFRC beams with FRP reinforcing bars

Type	Reference	Equations for shear capacity	
Beams with FRP rebars	ACI 440.1R-15 (2015)	$V_c = \frac{2}{5} \cdot \sqrt{f_c} \cdot b_w \cdot k \cdot d$ $k = \sqrt{2 \cdot \rho_f \cdot \eta_f + (\rho_f \cdot \eta_f)^2} - \rho_f \cdot \eta_f$	
	ACI 440.11 (2022)	$V_c = 0.066 \cdot \lambda_s \cdot \sqrt{f_c} \cdot b_w \cdot d$ $\lambda_s = \sqrt{\frac{2}{1 + 0.004 \cdot d}} \leq 1.0$ $\sqrt{f_c} \leq 8.3 \text{ MPa}$	
	CAN/CSA-S806 (2012)	$V_c = 0.05 \cdot \lambda \cdot \phi_c \cdot k_m \cdot k_r \cdot (f_c)^{1/3} \cdot b_w \cdot d_v$ $k_m = \sqrt{\frac{V_f \cdot d}{M_f}} \leq 1.0$ $k_r = 1 + (E_f \cdot \rho_f)^{1/3}$	
	CNR-DT203 (2006)	$V_{Rd,ct} = 1.3 \cdot \left(\frac{E_f}{E_c}\right)^{1/2} \cdot \tau_{Rd} \cdot k \cdot (1.2 + 40 \cdot \rho_1) \cdot b \cdot d$	
SFRC beams	FIB Model Code (2010) / ABNT NBR 16935 (2021)	$V_{Rd,F} = \left\{ \frac{0.18}{\gamma_c} \cdot k \cdot \left[100 \cdot \rho \cdot \left(1 + 7.5 \cdot \frac{f_{Ftu} k}{f_{ctk}} \right) \cdot f_{ck} \right]^{1/3} + 0.15 \cdot \sigma_{cp} \right\} \cdot b_w \cdot d$ $k = 1 + \sqrt{\frac{200}{d}} \leq 2.0$ $\rho = \frac{A_{sl}}{b_w \cdot d}$ $f_{Ftu} = f_{Fts} - \frac{w_u}{CMOD_3} \cdot (f_{Fts} - 0.5 \cdot f_{R3} + 0.2 \cdot f_{R1}) \geq 0$ $f_{Fts} = 0.45 \cdot f_{R1}$	
	RILEM TC 162-TDF (2003)	$V_{cd} = 0.12 \cdot k \cdot (100 \cdot \rho \cdot f_{ck})^{1/3} \cdot b_w \cdot d$ $V_{fd} = 0.7 \cdot k_f \cdot k \cdot \tau_{fd} \cdot b_w \cdot d$ $k_f = 1 + n \cdot \left(\frac{h_f}{b_w}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{h_f}{d}\right) \leq 1.5$ $n = \frac{b_f - b_w}{h_f} \leq 3 \text{ e } n \leq \frac{3 \cdot b_w}{h_f}$ $\tau_{fd} = 0.12 \cdot f_{Rk,4}$	
SFRC beams with FRP rebars	Tran, Pham and Hao (2020)	1	$V_c = \frac{2}{5} \cdot \sqrt{f_c} \cdot b \cdot c$ $c = k \cdot d$ $k = \sqrt{2 \cdot \rho_f \cdot \eta_f + (\rho_f \cdot \eta_f)^2} - \rho_f \cdot \eta_f$ $V_{fd} = 0.9 \cdot b \cdot d \cdot \sigma_p$ $\sigma_p = 0.41 \cdot \beta \cdot \tau_b \cdot V_f \cdot \frac{l_f}{d_f}$

			$\tau_b = 0.68 \cdot \sqrt{f_c}$ $V_u = V_c + V_{fd}$
		2	$V_c = \left(\frac{\rho_f \cdot E_f}{90 \cdot \beta_1} \right)^3 \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{f_c} \cdot b \cdot d}{6} \right)$ $\beta_1 = 0.85 - 0.05 \cdot \frac{f_c - 28}{7} \geq 0.65$ $V_u = V_c + V_{fd} \quad V_{fd} \text{ determined as in model 1}$
		3	$V_u = \left(\frac{0.3}{0.5 + (1000 \cdot \varepsilon_x + 0.15)^{0.7}} \cdot \frac{1300}{1000 + s_{xe}} \sqrt{f_c} + \sigma_p \cdot \cot \theta \right) \cdot b \cdot d_v$ $\sigma_p \text{ determined as in model 1}$ $\theta = (29^\circ + 7000 \cdot \varepsilon_x) \cdot \left(0.88 \cdot \frac{s_{xe}}{2500} \right) \leq 75^\circ$ $s_{xe} = \frac{31.5 \cdot d}{16 + d_a}$ $\varepsilon_x = V_u \cdot \frac{a - 0.5 \cdot d_v \cdot \cot \theta}{2 \cdot E_f \cdot A_f \cdot d_v}$
SFRC beams with FRP rebars	Hosseini, Nematzadeh and Chastre (2021)		$V_{R,F} = \left(0.16 \cdot f_c \cdot \frac{d}{a} \cdot \left(\frac{\rho_f \cdot E_f}{E_s} \right)^{0.23} + 0.066 \cdot \left(f_c \cdot \frac{a}{d} \right)^{0.54} \cdot (RI - 1) \right) b_w \cdot d$ $RI = \frac{V_f \cdot l_f}{d_f}$

Table 5: Comparison of shear strength of present test data with predictions of equations proposed by standard and others

Beam	V _{exp} (kN)	V _{ACI15} (kN)	V _{ACI22} (kN)	V _{CAN} (kN)	V _{CNR} (kN)	V _{NBR/VFIB} (kN)	V _{RILEM} (kN)	V _{HOS} (kN)	V _{TRAN} (kN)		
									1	2	3
CC0	31.7	14.55	22.19	33.68	41.25	46.66	46.66	52.27	13.10	13.26	40.22
SFRC0.50	63.35	14.95	22.19	34.06	41.81	67.98	68.18	71.10	42.10	43.68	52.86
SFRC0.75	68.65	14.34	22.19	33.22	40.56	72.81	75.78	72.69	54.62	53.06	57.89
SFRC1.00	76.0	13.73	22.19	33.44	40.89	74.03	77.04	82.25	69.07	68.22	63.79

V_{HOS}: model presented by Hosseini, Nematzadeh and Chastre (2021)
V_{TRAN}: model presented by Tran, Pham and Hao (2020)

Table 6: Ratio of shear strength of present test data with predictions of equations proposed by standard and others

Beam	V _{exp} /V _{ACI15}	V _{exp} /V _{ACI22}	V _{exp} /V _{CAN}	V _{exp} /V _{CNR}	V _{exp} /V _{NBR/VFIB}	V _{exp} /V _{RILEM}	V _{exp} /V _{HOS}	V _{exp} /V _{TRAN}		
								1	2	3
CC0	2.18	1.43	0.94	0.77	0.68	0.68	0.61	2.42	2.39	0.79
SFRC0.50	4.24	2.85	1.86	1.52	0.93	0.93	0.89	1.50	1.45	1.20
SFRC0.75	4.79	3.09	2.07	1.69	0.94	0.91	0.94	1.26	1.29	1.19
SFRC1.00	5.54	3.42	2.27	1.86	1.03	0.99	0.92	1.10	1.11	1.19
Average	4.18 (1.44)	2.70 (0.88)	1.79 (0.59)	1.46 (0.48)	0.90 (0.15)	0.88 (0.13)	0.84 (0.16)	1.57 (0.59)	1.56 (0.57)	1.09 (0.20)

Upon analyzing the results presented in Table 6 and Table 7, several observations can be made. For standards that estimate the shear capacity of beams reinforced with FRP bars, it is evident that CNR-DT203 (National Research Council, 2006) yielded the best results, followed by CAN/CSA S806-12 (Canadian Standards Association [CSA], 2012), ACI 440.11 (ACI, 2022) and ACI 440.1 R-15 (ACI, 2015). It should be noted that the ACI 440.11 (ACI, 2022) and ACI 440.1 R-15 (ACI, 2015) does not specifically address beams without stirrups, unlike the other standards.

In terms of standards estimating the shear strength of SFRC, NBR 16935 (ABNT, 2021), FIB Model Code (FIB, 2010), and RILEM (RILEM, 2003) demonstrated similar results. It is expected that these standards would yield higher shear strength compared to the experimental values since they pertain to elements reinforced with steel bars rather than the less rigid FRP bars.

Regarding the models proposed by researchers, which consider both the FRP bars and SFRC, it is observed that the three models proposed by Tran, Pham and Hao (2020) yielded conservative values, while the model proposed by Hosseini, Nematzadeh and Chastre (2021) overestimated the shear strength of the beams.

Among the models proposed by Tran, Pham and Hao (2020), Model 3 provided the best estimation for the shear strength of the beams. This model is based on modified compression field theory (MCFT) which considers the longitudinal strain in the middle of the cross section, the diagonal crack inclination and the spacing between the cracks as a function of the size of the aggregate. The contribution of the fiber is also considered. Consistent with this study, the conclusion aligns with Tran, Pham and Hao (2020) that MCFT is the most suitable method for calculating shear strength of SFRC elements using longitudinal FRP bars without stirrups.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions may be derived from the presented results and analysis.

1. The failure mode observed in most of the tested SFRC beams was shear failure with sudden rupture. For one beam, with fiber volume of 1.0%, a failure from shear to flexure-shear can be considered. Additionally, there was a significant similarity in the crack patterns among beams with the same fiber volumes.
2. Increasing the proportion of fiber volume resulted in upwards shifts of the load-deflection curves, indicating enhanced load capacity, stiffness, and vertical deflection at peak load of the beams. For instance, the SFRC1.00-2 beam exhibited an almost 300 % increase in load capacity compared to the CC0-1 beam. These results suggest that incorporating steel fibers may be an effective approach to improve the shear performance of concrete beams utilizing longitudinal FRP bars.
3. The study considered ten different models proposed by FRP and SFRC standards as well as researchers who combined FRP and SFRC. These models exhibited varying levels of accuracy when compared to the experimental results. Among them, Model 3 proposed by Tran, Pham and Hao (2020), which is based on Modified Compression Field Theory (MCFT), provided the best estimation of the shear strength for the experimental beams.

This study contributes to a better understanding of the shear performance of SFRC beams with GFRP rebars, providing valuable insights for structural design and strengthening applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank the Graduate Program in Civil Engineering at the Federal University of Paraná (PPGEC/UFPR), the Center for Civil Engineering Studies (CESEC) for the institutional support, the project CNPq/MCTI/FNDCT N° 18/2021 422189/2021-9 and the institutional project CAPES-PRINT/UFPR for the financial support.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- American Concrete Institute. (2007). *Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete and Commentary*. ACI 318-08. Farmington Hills.
- American Concrete Institute. (2015). *Guide for the Design and Construction of Structural Concrete Reinforced with Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Bars*. ACI 440.1R-15. Farmington Hills.
- American Concrete Institute. (2022). *Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete Reinforced with Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) Bars—Code and Commentary*. ACI 440.11. Farmington Hills.
- American Society for Testing and Materials. (2018). *Standard Specification for Portland Cement*. ASTM C150/C150M-18. West Conshohocken.
- American Society for Testing and Materials. (2016). *Standard test method for tensile properties of fiber reinforced polymer matrix composite bars*. ASTM D7205/D7205M-06. West Conshohocken.
- Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas. (2018). *Concreto - Ensaio de compressão de corpos de prova cilíndricos*. NBR 5739. Rio de Janeiro.
- Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas. (2021). *Concreto endurecido - Determinação dos módulos de elasticidade e de deformação. Parte 1: Módulos estáticos à compressão*. NBR 8522-1. Rio de Janeiro.
- Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas. (2017). *Concreto autoadensável - Parte 1: Classificação, controle e recebimento no estado fresco*. NBR 15823-1. Rio de Janeiro.
- Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas. (2017). *Concreto autoadensável - Parte 2: Determinação do espalhamento, do tempo de escoamento e do índice de estabilidade visual - Método do cone de Abrams*. NBR 15823-2. Rio de Janeiro.
- Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas. (2021). *Projeto de estruturas de concreto reforçado com fibras — Procedimento*. NBR 16935. Rio de Janeiro.
- Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas. (2021). *Concreto reforçado com fibras - Determinação das resistências à tração na flexão (limite de proporcionalidade e resistências residuais) - Método de ensaio*. NBR 16940. Rio de Janeiro.
- Aydın, E., Boru, E., & Aydın, F. (2021). Effects of FRP bar type and fiber reinforced concrete on the flexural behavior of hybrid beams. *Construction and Building Materials*, 279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.122407>
- Barros, J. A. O., & Foster, S. J. (2018). An integrated approach for predicting the shear capacity of fibre reinforced concrete beams. *Engineering Structures*, 174(January), 346–357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2018.07.071>
- Canadian Standards Association. (2017). *Design and construction of building structures with fibre-reinforced polymers*. CSA S806-12. 2 Ed.: Canadian Standards Association.
- Federation Internationale du Beton. (2010). *FIB Model Code for Concrete Structures. FIB Model Code 2010*. MC 2010. Lausanne: FIB. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783433604090>.
- Ferrier, E., Michel, L., Zuber, B., & Chanvillard, G. (2015). Mechanical behaviour of ultra-high-performance short-fibre-reinforced concrete beams with internal fibre reinforced polymer bars. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 68, 246–258. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2014.08.001>
- Hosseini, S.-A., Nematzadeh, M., & Chastre, C. (2021). Prediction of shear behavior of steel fiber-reinforced rubberized concrete beams reinforced with glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars. *Composite Structures*, 256, 113010. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.113010>
- Imam, M., Vandewalle, L., Mortelmans, F., & Van Gemert, D. (1997). Shear domain of fibre-reinforced high-strength concrete beams. *Engineering Structures*, 19(9), 738–747. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296\(96\)00150-2](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296(96)00150-2)
- Jafarzadeh, H., & Nematzadeh, M. (2020). Evaluation of post-heating flexural behavior of steel fiber-reinforced high-strength concrete beams reinforced with FRP bars: Experimental and analytical results. *Engineering Structures*, 225, 111292. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.111292>

- Nanni, A.; De Luca, A.; Zadeh, H. (2014). *Reinforced Concrete with FRP Bars: Mechanics and Design*. London: CRC Press.
- National Research Council. Advisory Committee on Technical Recommendations for Design and Construction. (2006). *Guide for the design and construction of concrete structures reinforced with fiber-reinforced polymer bars*. CNR-DT 203. Rome.
- Réunion Internationale Des Laboratoires et Experts des Matériaux. (2003). *Test and design methods for steel fibre reinforced concrete sigma-epsilon design method*. RILEM TC 162-TDF. Paris, RILEM.
- Soltanzadeh, F., Behbahani, A. E., Mazaheripour, H., & Barros, J. A. O. (2016). Shear resistance of SFRSCC short-span beams without transversal reinforcements. *Composite Structures*, *139*, 42–61. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.11.067>
- Tran, T. T., Pham, T. M., & Hao, H. (2020). Effect of hybrid fibers on shear behaviour of geopolymer concrete beams reinforced by basalt fiber reinforced polymer (BFRP) bars without stirrups. *Composite Structures*, *243*, 112236. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.112236>
- Vakili, S. E., Homami, P., & Esfahani, M. R. (2019). Effect of fibers and hybrid fibers on the shear strength of lightweight concrete beams reinforced with GFRP bars. *Structures*, *20*, 290–297. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2019.04.006>
- Yoo, D.-Y., Banthia, N., & Yoon, Y.-S. (2016a). Predicting service deflection of ultra-high-performance fiber-reinforced concrete beams reinforced with GFRP bars. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, *99*, 381–397. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2016.06.013>
- Yoo, D.-Y., Banthia, N., & Yoon, Y.-S. (2016b). Flexural behavior of ultra-high-performance fiber-reinforced concrete beams reinforced with GFRP and steel rebars. *Engineering Structures*, *111*, 246–262. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2015.12.003>